

FEATURES OF FORMATION DAMAGE BRAIN FROM INFLUENCE OF BLUNT OBJECTS

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ANNOTATION

In the article, in order to identify the characteristics of the formation of injury during blunt mechanical injury, depending on the properties of the objects, the nature of damage to the brain bones in 12 people who died from severe traumatic brain injury (TBI). In all cases, in addition to the forensic medical examination of corpses, a histological study was carried out using modern methods. It was established that the nature of the time brain have from the properties and characteristics of the impacting surface of blunt objects, direct impact which are formed by local destruction of the integrity of these bones.

Key words: diagnosis and mechanism brain damage.

Relevance: Forensic for assessment mechanism of injury and identification of brain damage. For various types of blunt trauma it is of interest to study morphological features of skin lesions head and skull bones. It is believed that the features traumatic weapons in some cases clearly affect damage to these structures, most severely in the bones skulls [1.P.51-54; 6.P.143-146; 5. P.175-180]. Fractures of the bones of the vault and skull base may be isolated and combined. Fractures of the parietal and frontal bone are observed much more often than fractures in occipital and temporal bones. Nature of cranial vault fractures may be in the form of linear fractures, cracks and depressed fractures. In the brains of the foundation in some cases, for example, when falling from a height onto your feet diffuse blood effusions form, fractures around the large occipital foramen. Depending on the application location traumatic force is distinguished by local - direct fractures in place of application of traumatic force, locally structural and structural - indirect (away from the site application of force) fractures of the skull bones. For morphology fractures are influenced by the nature of the impacting surface objects - limited, spherical, dominant, cylindrical, etc. Local destruction leads to the formation of cracks, linear, curvilinear, perforated fractures [2. 24 S.; 4. 240 S.; 3.248 WITH.]. Purpose of the study. Identification of formation features fractures of the skull bones and cerebral hemorrhage due to blunt mechanical trauma, in depending on the properties of traumatic blunt solid objects.

Materials and methods of research. Character and features of the formation of damage to the head structure in 12 - of those people who died from severe traumatic brain injury (TBI) in as a result of exposure to blunt hard objects that have various impact surfaces. In all cases there was a forensic medical examination of corpses and a medical -histological and forensic examination of the skull was carried out, in a number of cases and skin and muscle tissue of the head.

Results of the study and their discussions. For solutions forensic tasks to identify the mechanism and tools the most informative were the nature and formation of fractures of the bones of the cranial vault. However, at the same time the characteristics of skin and soft injuries were also taken into account head tissues. Analysis of damage research results

structures of the head were carried out taking into account the characteristics of the impacting surface of traumatic blunt hard objects, which fatal head injuries were caused to the dead 12 persons.

1. Features of the formation of the shape of damage to the vault of the skull bones from the impact of blunt objects having the shape limited round surface, can be shown on the following example. Citizen, 32 years old, was injured in as a result of a simultaneous blunt impact a solid object having a limited rounded surface. Death occurred at the scene of the event from TBI In this case, on the skin flap of the parietal region of the deceased M.I., a bruised lacerated wound was revealed, in the same area on the frontal There is a depressed fracture of the bone. Morphological indicators injuries, the nature of the fractures and the condition of the brain and hemorrhage, fracture of the outer and inner bone plates made it possible to note that these damages occurred simultaneously as a result of impact of a blunt hard object with limited surface, which was confirmed data from the case materials.

2. Features of the formation of fractures of the skull bones from the impact of blunt objects with a predominant surface, can be shown using the following example: Citizen A. R suffered blow to the head with a blunt hard object. In this case, it was revealed that a linear fracture of the right parietal bones formed by the type of deformation during combination of local destruction, expansion and bending with impaired cerebral circulation . Character and features of the fracture called to establish that it was formed as a result of the impact of a blunt hard object with flat dominant surface. In all observations, the deceased had manifestations

severe TBI with damage to the integrity of the meninges and substances of the brain, and therefore death in victims were observed at the scene and in hospitals.

Conclusions. The nature of damage to the head structure during blunt force injury depends on the properties and characteristics impact surface of blunt hard objects, the direct impact of which forms local destruction of the integrity of the bones of the cranial vault. However , At the same time, bone fractures can also form in structures of the base of the skull. In case of fatal TBI in conditions of non-obvious circumstances of injury application modern methods of medical and forensic research fully allow us to assess the mechanism of injury, up to establishing the properties of the damaged area of the brain and directions of impact. The described types of damage must be taken into account in the forensic medical process. research to establish the mechanism and instrument of injury.

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